

Study on *p*-t-Butylphenol—Formaldehyde modified Drying Oil Alkyds

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p-t-Butylphenol—formaldehyde modified drying oil alkyds have been prepared and characterised for specific industrial applications. The viscous liquids obtained involve the Diels—Alder reaction during modification of drying oil alkyds with the phenolic resin is indicated by IR studies. The resins possess characteristic resistance of phenolics towards chemicals in addition to the outstanding durability, greater flexibility and resistance to yellowing. TGA studies show sufficient improvement in heat resistance of the alkyds after modification.

ALKYD resins are generally manufactured by using phthalic anhydride, glycerol and vegetable oil, monoglycerides or fatty acids. This product is of little value in itself and it is only when modifying ingredients are introduced, the valuable synthetic resins are produced. Drying oil fatty acid modified alkyds are used more widely than any other modifications¹. Phenolic resins, although give body, strength, toughness, resistance to moisture and chemicals for surface coatings, they lack in flexibility because of inherent brittleness and have less air-drying and film-forming properties. They are also unstable in solvents or thinners because of low solubility. Further, they yellow on exposure to light and impart poor gloss. They are also handicapped in electrical applications. These drawbacks may be overcome by modifying these resins with drying oils and alkyds. Similarly, alkyds, which have outstanding durability, sufficient flexibility and solubility in oils and other organic solvents, suffer badly with the inherent poor resistance to water, acids, alkalies and other chemicals, and may be modified with PTBP resin with a view to incorporate the characteristic water, alkali and chemical resistance in the modified product.

As the modification of phenolic resins with suitable materials may give products adopted for diverse and often stringent engineering applications, it was thought quite fruitful to prepare any modified resins in search of better products for specific industrial applications. In this communication, preparation and characterisation of *p*-t-butylphenol—formaldehyde (PTBPF) modified linseed and dehydrated castor oil alkyds have been reported.

Experimental

Preparation of castor and linseed oil alkyds: All the chemicals, viz. phthalic anhydride (0.89 mol), glycerine (0.52 mol), malic anhydride (0.02 mol), castor oil (220 g), toluol (198.5 g), Co-octate

(0.50 g), Pb-naphthenate (0.75 g) and Mn-octate (0.50 g), used for the preparation of castor oil alkyd were of high purity; while the chemicals used for the preparation of linseed oil alkyd were phthalic anhydride (0.73 mol), glycerine (0.74 mol), linseed oil fatty acids (184 g), toluol (140 g), Co-octate (0.50 g), Pb-naphthenate (0.75 g) and Mn-octate (0.50 g).

Method: All the ingredients were taken in the reaction flask and a stream of nitrogen was passed through the mixture at a rate of $10 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$, and the flow rate was maintained until the resin was ready for discharge from the flask. The rate of nitrogen flow was checked with gas flow meter. The temperature of the charge was raised to 180° in approximately 1 h and then allowed to stand at that temperature for 1 h. The source of heat was then cut off and the condenser removed, while N_2 still allowed to bubble through the U-tube take-off was replaced directly into side-neck. The temperature was raised to 245° for approximately 1.5 h or until the acid value reached below 8 mg KOH/g of the resin. Linseed oil alkyd was also prepared in the same manner.

Alkyd resins so obtained were used for modification of phenolic resins. To test various properties of the alkyd resins, they were cooled down to 70° and then thinner toluol followed by driers were added. Varnishes so prepared were not air-drying but of stoving type

Preparation of p-t-butylphenolic resin modified with linseed oil or castor oil alkyds: Linseed oil modified *p*-t-butylphenolic resin was prepared using linseed oil alkyd resin (75 g), *p*-t-butylphenolic resin (25 g), butanol (10 g), cellosolve (10 g), diacetone (10 g), light solvent (70 g), Co-octate (0.50 g), Pb-naphthenate (0.75 g) and Mn-octate (0.50 g); while castor oil modified *p*-t-butylphenolic resin was prepared using the same chemicals except for castor oil alkyd (75 g) in place of linseed oil alkyd.

In a reaction kettle fitted with a stirrer and a thermometer, the linseed oil alkyd or castor oil alkyd resin (75 g) was heated upto 90° with constant stirring for about 5 min in presence of inert gas (N₂). Then, *p*-t-butylphenolic resin (25 g) was gradually added in small portions. At the beginning, the temperature was allowed to rise slowly. When the mixture become completely homogeneous, the temperature was raised to 190° and maintained for 45 min. When acid value approached the desired value, the resin became so viscous that it was difficult to proceed further reaction. At that stage, it was cooled to 70° and blended with 50% solvents followed by the addition of driers. The varnish so obtained was of stoving type.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis of LO and DCO alkyds : Esters are common constituents of alkyds, especially in the form of triglycerides, such as vegetable oils. Probably this is the reason for drying oil fatty acids being used for modification of alkyds. Most commonly used vegetable oils are linseed and dehydrated castor oils, both having very high percentage (90-99.5%) of unsaturated acid triglyceroides.

The mechanism of the reactions involved during the resin formation has been studied by many workers²⁻⁷. Organic acids can react with compounds containing hydroxyl group, eliminating water and forming an ester link between the molecules. Alkyds are formed by the reaction of polyacids with polyhydroxy compounds. The reaction of the synthesis of oil modified alkyds takes place in two steps (Scheme 1). The first step in the synthesis of an alkyd is the alcoholysis of oil (triglyceride of fatty acids) to form monoglycerides. The monoglycerides and the remaining glycerol then react with phthalic anhydride yielding the alkyd resin. The occurrence of reactive sites in

alkyds offers tremendous potential for chemical modification with reactive monomers and other polyfunctional building blocks. In the molecule of the alkyd, R is the fatty acid chain which may contain conjugated or non-conjugated unsaturation. These linkages are the major sites for modifications of alkyds. There may be three possible types of reaction which might occur, *viz.* radical⁸, ionic⁹ and chain transfer¹⁰. The most accepted one is the Diels-Alder reaction suggesting a reaction between PTBP and the unsaturation sites present in the oil.

Properties of the modified resins :

Various properties of the modified resins are recorded in Tables 1-3. The PTBP modified vegetable oil alkyds have an advantage, that they have characteristic resistance of phenolics for various chemicals.

Cure time, gel time, hardness and flexibility : PTBP modified vegetable oil alkyds are not air-drying, but of stoving type. The gel time is higher for LOAL-PTBP (7.5 h) than for DCOAL-PTBP (5.5 h) (Table 1). The drying time at 140° is similarly higher for LO-resin (1 h) as compared to that for the DCO-resin (45 min) (Table 1). The values of surface-dry, hard-dry and tack-free tests are higher for the PTBP modified alkyds as compared to that for the unmodified vegetable oil alkyds (Table 1). However, these values are relatively low for the DCO-resin (compared to that for the LO-resin). The value of scratch hardness is same for both the modified and the unmodified LO-alkyds. However, it is less for the modified, than the unmodified DCO-alkyd. Flexibility value on modification with PTBP increases in case of LO-alkyd, while decreases in case of the corresponding DCO-resin. The values of gloss have been found unchanged on the modification while the cure in thick section was found satisfactory in case of the modified LO-alkyd, a few wrinkles were noticed in case of the modified DCO-alkyd.

Dielectric constant : On modification with PTBP, the value of dielectric constant was found to increase in case of LO-alkyd, but it was found to decrease in case of the DCO-alkyd. However, the values of breakdown voltage under all the experimental conditions was found decreasing in PTBP modified alkyds (Table 1).

Thermal analysis : The results of TGA analysis are given in Tables 2 and 3. A representative TGA diagram for DCOAL resin is presented in Fig. 1. The decomposition temperatures and the temperature at which the rate of decomposition is maximum are in Table 2, whereas the temperatures at which 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50% decomposition of the resins take place, are recorded in Table 3.

LO alkyd has a temperature of initial decomposition of 289° which is found to improve to 300° on modification with PTBP resin. This indicates that the composite made out of alkyd and phenolic

Scheme 1. Synthesis of the PTBP modified resins.

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF MODIFIED ALKYD RESINS

Sl. no.	Property	LOAL	DCO-AL	LOAL-PTBP	DCO-ALPTBP
1.	Physical state	Viscous	Viscous	Viscous	Viscous
2.	Colour	Light brown	Brown	Light brown	Light brown
3.	Solubility	Xylene, toluene mineral terpentine	Xylene, toluene	Butanol, cyclohexanol	Xylol, toluol mineral terpentine
4.	Viscosity (in F.C. 4 cup)	24 s	30 s	35 s	27 s
5.	Sp. gravity	0.93	0.98	1.93	0.96
6.	Non-volatile content (%)	42.5	53	57.4	50.2
7.	Acid value (mg KOH/g)	5.3	6.1	2.9	2.8
8.	Drying time (air-dry)	Overnight	Not air-drying	Not air-drying	Not air-drying
9.	Drying time (min) (stoving at 140°)	30	15	60	45
	Surface-dry (min)	15	8	30	25
	Hard-dry (min)	20	12	45	38
	Tack-free (min)	30	15	60	45
10.	Scratch hardness (g)	2 000	1 600	2 000	1 200
11.	Flexibility (mm)	10.7	10.6	11.1	10.1
12.	Gloss	>100	>100	>100	>100
13.	Cure in thick section	Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Few wrinkless
14.	Dielectric constant (kV mm ⁻¹)	22	28	25	23
15.	Breakdown voltage (kW mm ⁻¹)				
	At room temp.	88.06	78.02	86.1	72.2
	At 130°	46.9	39.9	40.2	39.1
	At room temp. after immersion in water for 24 h	16.2	14.9	15.1	13.9

TABLE 2—DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE AND TEMPERATURE OF MAXIMUM DECOMPOSITION RATES OF THE MODIFIED RESINS

Sl. no.	Resin	Decomp. temp. °C	Temp. of maximum decomp. °C
1.	DCO-Alkyd	295	460
2.	LO-Alkyd	289	480
3.	PTBPF-DCO Alkyd	300	460
4.	PTBPF-LO Alkyd	300	475

TABLE 3—FRACTIONAL WEIGHT LOSS TEMPERATURE OF MODIFIED ALKYD RESINS

Sl. no.	Resin	Temperature °C				
		10%	20%	30%	40%	50%
1.	LOALK	295	310	320	330	340
2.	DCOALK	340	370	390	410	430
3.	PTBPF-DCOALK	325	350	375	395	420
4.	PTBPF-LOALK	310	325	340	355	375

Fig. 1. Thermogram of DCOAL resin.

resins has better heat resistance than either of the resins studied separately. DCO-based alkyd has shown an initial weight loss temperature of about 300° (295°), which is higher than that of LO-alkyd (289°). This is due to the use of isophthalic acid in the particular formulation, which is known to have higher heat resistance. Examination of the temperatures at which the initial decomposition starts indicates that the temperature (300°) shown by these

PTBP modified alkyds is the highest amongst the resins studied in this investigation.

Ir spectra: The characteristic absorption bands obtained from ir spectra in each of the resin are recorded in Table 4. Spectra of LO-alkyd is characterised by the presence of a doublet at 1 600 cm⁻¹ which is attributed to orthophthalate ester. This is further supported by the presence of peak at 740 cm⁻¹, which characterises 1 : 2 disubstitution of benzene ring and ring bending mode at 700 cm⁻¹. Three strong bands at ~1 280, 1 140

TABLE 4—CHARACTERISTIC IR BANDS OF MODIFIED RESINS

Sl. no.	Resin	ν_{\max} cm^{-1}
1.	LO-ALK	3 700 - 3 200 bb vs, 2 960s, 2 880s, 2 700sh, 1 740vs, 1 610, 1 580s, 1 450, 1 380, 1 300m, 1 300s, 1 280, 1 170, 1 140s, 1 070m, 980s, 910s, 850m, 770m, 740m 700m, 655m, 530m, 250vs
2.	DCO.ALK	3 500 - 3 440 bb s, 2 960, 2 880s, 2 700sh, 1 740vs, 1 610s, 1 450, 1 380, 1 300m, 1 230m, 1 170, 1 140m, 1 090, 1 070m, 995s, 980s, 850sh, 720vs, 655m, 250vs
3.	PTBPF-LOALK	3 700 - 3 100 bb s, 2 940vs, 2 880s, 1 740m, 1 600, 1 580m, 1 490m, 1 460, 1 450m, 1 380vs, 1 330, 1 287vs, 1 120vs, 1 070vs, 1 040s, 990s, 920w, 880m, 820m, 740, 700m, 650m, 560m, 250vs
4.	PTBPF-DCO.ALK	3 700 - 3 100 bb vs, 2 960, 2 880s, 1 720vs, 1 610vs, 1 490m, 1 460m, 1 380m, 1 300, 1 230m, 1 120w, 1 070s, 1 000s, 940m, 880vs, 820vs, 720vs, 650m, 550m, 250vs

and $1\,070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are also characteristic of orthophthalate ester. A broad band near $1\,170\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to aliphatic ester due to linseed oil. Spectra of DCO alkyd representing an isophthalate alkyd is clearly different from that of LO alkyd in the following points : (i) only a single peak is seen near $1\,600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, (ii) a band is visible at 720 cm^{-1} as against 740 cm^{-1} in the spectra of LO alkyd,

(iii) ring banding mode is not present at 700 cm^{-1} , and (iv) bands attributable to aromatic ester are present at $1\,300$, $1\,230$ and a doublet near $1\,075\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is different from orthophthalate ester pattern. Ir spectra of PTBP modified LO and DCO alkyds show broad and strong hydroxyl band near $3\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characterising the presence of phenolic hydroxyl group.

It is seen that LO alkyd is based on orthophthalic ester, while DCO alkyd is based on isophthalate ester. The difference already discussed above, is also revealed here in the modified resins. However, the presence of *para*-substituted-phenolic resin is indicated by the two medium intensity bands at 820 and 875 cm^{-1} in both the modified resins. This clearly shows that there has been no decomposition of phenolic hydroxyls, and the phenolic resin is present in the formulations prepared.

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